

ATU Research Showcase

Meet ATU's Education Researchers

Advancing Research-Led Teaching & Learning Across Ireland and Beyond

Ollscoil
Teicneolaíochta
an Atlantaigh

Atlantic
Technological
University

**Research,
Innovation and
Engagement**

United Nations

International Day of Education
24 January

This booklet was compiled and designed by the ATU Research Coordinator Team, Dr Shane Conway, Dr James Britton, Dr Alan Naughton & Dr Alan Heron, and funded through RISE@ATU.

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An tÚdarás um Ard-Oideachas
The Higher Education Authority

Meet ATU's Education Researchers

Enhancing Educational Practice and Innovation Across Ireland and Beyond

To mark the United Nations International Day of Education 2026 (January 24th), which celebrates the power of youth and learners in co-creating education, the Research Coordinator team at Atlantic Technological University (ATU), funded through RISE@ATU, presents the third edition of the ATU Research Showcase Series. This edition highlights the work of ATU researchers whose scholarship is advancing educational practice, innovation and social transformation through research.

Spanning inclusive education, digital pedagogies, education for sustainable development, wellbeing, creative methodologies and evidence-informed teaching practice, this Showcase illustrates how education research at ATU is responding to contemporary challenges facing learners, educators and communities across the west and north-west of Ireland and beyond. It reflects interdisciplinary research and collaboration across ATU's faculties and Research Centres, where educational research is closely connected to practice, policy and societal impact.

As the technological university for the west and north-west, ATU grounds its education research in regional, national and international priorities. In alignment with Ireland's National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) for Innovation 2022–2027 and the UN Sustainable Development Goals, ATU contributes to strengthening inclusive, equitable and future-focused education systems at a time of rapid technological, social and economic change.

This booklet presents a representative sample of 12 researchers whose profiles demonstrate ATU's growing expertise in education research that meaningfully engages students, educators and communities in shaping learning futures. Their work highlights the importance of co-creation, inclusivity and innovation in education. Many other colleagues across ATU are making equally valuable contributions in this field, and this Showcase is intended to reflect a cross-section of that collective strength rather than provide an exhaustive account.

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ATU Campus Locations

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Byrne**

**Dr John
Scahill**

**Dr Carina
Ginty**

**Dr Gerry
McWilliams**

**Dr Shane
Wilson**

**Dr Tamsin
Cavaliero**

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Research

Research,
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Engagement

Education Researchers

Innovation Across Ireland and Beyond

Showcase

Dr Deirdre Byrne

*Inclusive, Wellbeing-centred Research for Education,
Policy and Practice*

Dr Deirdre Byrne is a Staff Researcher at ATU Sligo, working across the Social Sciences, Marketing, Tourism and Sport. Deirdre holds an Irish Research Council-funded PhD in Sociology and was previously a Research Fellow at TUS Athlone, where she authored

ATU Sligo

Ireland's National Student Mental Health and Suicide Prevention Framework and led wellbeing curriculum initiatives in higher education.

At ATU, Dr Byrne plays a central role in developing funding proposals and managing national and European research projects. Her research focuses on inclusive, sustainable, and socially responsive approaches across social care innovation, wellbeing, inclusive education and sustainable tourism, with a strong emphasis on policy-relevant and practice-based research. Nationally, Deirdre has contributed to studies on autism and education, sustainable shared spaces, and embedding wellbeing across the higher education curriculum. Her recent work, funded by AsIAm – Ireland's National Autism Charity, explores the educational experiences of autistic children and young people in Ireland, amplifying the voices of students and their families. At European level, Dr Byrne is involved in several EU-funded projects spanning social care innovation (e.g. TechSocialCare) and sustainable tourism (e.g. ATLANTIC BRIDGES). Deirdre is also an active member of the Sustainable Tourism and Visitor Experience Lab (STORY ATU) and supported ATU's successful membership bid to become a UN Tourism Sustainable Tourism Observatory.

Dr Perry Share

Future-proofing Social Professional Education with Digital Technologies

Dr Perry Share is Head of the School of Social Science and Humanities at ATU. He is a sociologist, investigating social robotics, the sociology of food and drink and education policy and practice. Dr Share is pioneering the integration of artificial intelligence (AI), virtual

ATU Sligo/ATU Mayo

reality (VR) and social robotics in the education of social professionals, preparing them for a future with these rapidly advancing technologies. In close collaboration with Dr John Pender (ATU Sligo) Perry has implemented a range of approaches to engage learners with and understand the potential use-cases of autonomous technologies. Utilising 'tinkering' robotics design workshops, VR caregiving, AI-driven simulations and MOOCs (free online courses) Perry and John study student engagement with social care scenarios in safe environments and the use of AI in decision-making in care situations.

Human-Robot Interaction (HRI) is a key focus of this work. The Blossom Social Robot Initiative explored the student-led design of robot behaviour, gaining insights into HRI relationships and potential ethical implications. This has been extended through involvement in European collaborative projects PROSPERO (pedagogy of social robots – Erasmus+) and TechSocCare (regulation of assistive technologies – Interreg Europe). By combining their observations with insights and experiences of the learners, Dr Share and Dr Pender seek to identify novel methods to facilitate learners' development of critical skills for the future.

Dr John Scahill

Promoting Education for Sustainable Development in Teaching and Learning.

Dr John Scahill is a Lecturer and Researcher in the Department of Building and Civil Engineering at ATU Galway and co-lead of the Education for Sustainable Development Academy. His research focuses on advancing sustainability in higher education, with particular emphasis

ATU Galway

on Education for Sustainable Development, the UN Sustainable Development Goals, circular economy transitions and digitally enhanced pedagogical innovation. Dr Scahill is Principal Investigator on the EU GREEN BASE project, a multi-university research initiative examining sustainability-related education practices and perceptions among academic staff across nine European partner universities. This work contributes to strengthening institutional capacity for sustainability education through evidence-based insights and cross-institutional collaboration.

A core strand of Dr Scahill's research explores interdisciplinary collaboration and co-creation as mechanisms for embedding sustainability within curricula and institutional practice, including the Change Laboratory approach as a tool for organisational and educational transformation. Dr Scahill is also a member of ATU's OSCAR (Operations and Supply Chain Research) Research Unit and contributes to the Build360 Hub, a national collaboration supporting the transition to a decarbonised and circular construction sector through research, education and industry engagement. John was also ATU's Coordinator on the Digital Academy for a Sustainable Built Environment (DASBE), a Human Capital Initiative (HCI) funded programme.

Dr Anne-Marie Clarke

*Digital Storytelling for
Teaching and Learning*

Dr Anne-Marie Clarke is a Lecturer in Education at ATU whose research centres on Digital Storytelling as an innovative pedagogy for teaching and learning across primary and post-primary education. Her work explores how creative, narrative-based digital practices can

ATU Galway

enhance learner engagement, ownership of knowledge, and cross-curricular understanding, particularly within science and the arts. Dr Clarke led 'The Art of Science' (AoSP), a Government of Ireland-funded, three-year research intervention under Ireland's National Digital Strategy. The project investigated the use of Digital Storytelling in cross-curricular (art and science) and cross-sectoral (primary and post-primary) contexts across five Irish schools, with findings published in *Irish Educational Studies* in June 2025. Teachers were trained to support learners in creating original digital stories based on scientific concepts using student-generated artwork. The research demonstrated deeper conceptual understanding, increased collaboration, and stronger real-world connections for learners. Her doctoral research, completed at Queen's University Belfast, examined teachers' development of Instructional Digital Stories (IDS) across the curriculum using a situated learning framework. This work was subsequently published in the *Universal Journal of Educational Research* in 2017. Dr Clarke also holds a Research Master's degree from Trinity College Dublin and has extensive experience facilitating Digital Storytelling workshops in educational and community settings, contributing to research-informed innovation in teaching practice.

Dr Carina Ginty

*Transformative Education and Sustainable Learning
Futures*

Dr Carina Ginty is Head of Teaching and Learning at ATU, where she leads initiatives in GenAI, transformative education, sustainable learning and digital pedagogies in higher education.

With over 20 years' experience, she has

ATU Galway

spearheaded national and international projects focused on assessment enhancement, digital transformation and student partnership.

From 2022–2025, Carina served as ATU Lead for N-TUTORR Transforming Learning (NextGenerationEU, €40m), co-leading the national workstream on student empowerment and partnership in higher education. She previously led ATU's transition to digital teaching during COVID-19 and developed DigitalEd.ie under the HEA-funded iNOTE project (€2.9m). Currently, she co-leads ATU's Learning Ecosystem Project (€6m) and serves as Academic Lead for MyCareerPath.ie under the HigherEd 4.0 initiative, transforming access to higher education.

Dr Ginty supervises postgraduate research in education science, digital teaching, and educational psychology, and chairs ATU's Learning, Teaching and Assessment Committee of Academic Council (2022–26). She also represents ATU on the EU GREEN Alliance Education Commission, leading the pedagogical development programme across nine partner universities. In recognition of her leadership, Carina received ATU's President's Award for Outstanding Institutional Citizenship (2022) and was awarded Principal Fellowship of Advance HE (PFHEA) in 2025.

Mary Nolan

Humanising Engineering Education through Ethics of Care

Mary Nolan is a Lecturer in Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering and an Academic Developer. She is also a PhD researcher exploring ethics of care in engineering education. Mary examines how engineering decisions shape daily life and human flourishing, and how care-based, participatory approaches support more inclusive and responsible practice.

ATU Sligo

She contributes to a European review on ethics of care in engineering education and an international review of Community-Based Participatory Inclusive Design (CBPID), a methodology she co-developed with colleagues from ATU, UCD and Thomas Jefferson University to integrate lived experience into design and research. Mary is Vice-Chair of the Engineers Ireland Academic Society and has led international workshops on ethics of care, with publications in SEFI and IEEE EDUCON.

Mary's research applies CBPID in collaboration with the Anne Sullivan Association for the Deafblind, co-developing a narrative case study showing how engineered systems can include or exclude people and how power operates through design. This will inform teaching at ATU, where students explore lived experience as ethical insight. Using LEGO Serious Play and an ethics of care lens, students examine how design choices impact people's lives, strengthening ATU's leadership in inclusive, socially responsible engineering education.

Dr Gerry McWilliams

*Cyberpsychology and Evidence-based,
Student-focused Practice in Education*

Dr Gerry McWilliams is a Lecturer in Cyberpsychology in ATU Donegal. Gerry has 20 years' experience as an educator and researcher across Ireland and the UK, in both the public and private sectors. His work spans training design, programme delivery, and leading

ATU Donegal

people and systems, with a consistent focus on supporting vulnerable learners and communities. Gerry completed a Master's in Behavioural Psychology from Ulster University, and subsequently earned his PhD there, focusing on evidence-based practice in teaching and education.

Dr McWilliams has published in the Journal of Behavioural Education, investigating the use of Early Reading software to improve reading performance in disadvantaged children, demonstrating significant improvements in reading. Gerry is also a researcher in the Erasmus+ funded HealthCraft project, using the videogame Minecraft to teach healthy habits to primary school children, investigating how the benefits of mental wellbeing and sleep can be taught meaningfully. A key strength of Gerry's is designing and delivering student-centred training. Over the past five years, Gerry has designed and taught on ATU's undergraduate and postgraduate Cyberpsychology programmes, and he currently supervises several student research projects in this rapidly developing field. Gerry recently presented at the University of Oxford on the intersection of cybersecurity and cyberpsychology, with a paper arising from this work due for publication.

Dr Ann Marie Casserly

Evidence-Based Research in Special and Inclusive Education

Dr Ann Marie Casserly is Head of the Education Department at ATU St. Angelas and Director of the Centre for Special Educational Needs, Inclusion and Diversity. Her research focuses on inclusive pedagogies in multigrade classrooms, dyslexia, SNA Training, Universal Design for

ATU St. Angelas

Learning (UDL), professional learning for teachers and policy-informed practice in inclusive education. She also researches behaviour, anxiety and social media use among university students.

Dr Casserly holds a PhD in Education from Queen's University Belfast and has led and contributed to a wide range of funded programme/research totalling €500,000 supported by bodies including the National Council for Special Education (NCSE), the Standing Conference on Teacher Education, North and South (SCoTENS) and Meirici funding. She is currently involved in the NCSE Practice-Based Research Programme (2023–2026), strengthening the connection between research evidence, classroom practice, and national policy development. Her research outputs include over 80 peer-reviewed journal articles and conference proceedings. Her ongoing research examines the impact of inclusive teacher professional learning programmes and UDL implementation in higher education. Dr Casserly serves on many Editorial Advisory Boards (e.g. Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs) and acts as a reviewer for 10 leading peer-reviewed journals including the International Journal of Inclusive Education.

Dr Shane Wilson

Future-proofing Engineering Education in an GenAI Landscape

Dr Shane Wilson, SFHEA, is a Lecturer in Computer Science in the Department of Computing at ATU Letterkenny, with over 28 years' experience in higher education across Ireland and the UK. His work focuses on researching and applying innovative

ATU Donegal

approaches to teaching and learning in computer science and related disciplines. He has received a number of teaching awards recognising excellence in educational practice, and prior to joining ATU was awarded a Distinguished Teaching Fellowship at Ulster University for innovation in teaching.

The rise in remote education has brought challenges as well as opportunities. Since joining ATU Dr Wilson has investigated the use of digital technologies and pedagogical enhancements such as flipped classroom and UDL to enhance the teaching and learning experiences of both on campus and remote learners at ATU.

Dr Wilson is a co-supervisor in the RISE@ATU funded THRIVE PRTP where his student is researching how training the elderly and health care professionals using virtual reality and artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance the well-being of older people.

Dr Wilson's current research focuses on the impact of AI on teaching and learning, exploring challenges around the transparent, ethical and efficient use of AI to enhance the teaching and learning experience whilst ensuring academic integrity.

Dr Dermot O'Donovan

Advancing Education for Sustainable Development through Research and Applied Design

Dr Dermot O'Donovan is Head of the Department of Creative Education in the School of Creative Industries. Dermot's research sits at the intersection of education, sustainability and applied design, with a particular focus on circular economy skills, Education for

ATU Connemara

Sustainable Development (ESD). and research-informed professional practice. Dermot was awarded a PhD from Lancaster University in 2020, focussing on ESD in Irish Higher Education Institutions. He has led out on several successful Erasmus+ projects for ATU, including FLIER, WOODCircle and WOODigital - awarded 'Best Practice' by the French National Agency. These projects have supported the twin transition, digital and green, within a European context in both education and industry. Dermot is coordinating an IRC New Foundations project between ATU and University of Galway, which aims to embed Global Citizenship Education within initial teacher education programmes.

Dr O'Donovan is co-supervisor of PhD researcher Maria Moore, whose research examines the structural and institutional factors that affect student teachers' engagement in action research during school placement. Dermot has presented his research at conferences in Ireland, UK, Finland, Spain, and South Africa. Dermot also contributes to ATU Connemara's Green Campus Committee which spearheaded the Community Native Woodland initiative, involving the planting of over 6,000 native trees on a 5-acre site in Connemara National Park since 2013.

Dr Tamsin Cavaliero

*Inclusive Education Approaches, Graphic Facilitation
and Creative Methodologies*

Dr Tamsin Cavaliero is a Lecturer in the Department of Social Sciences at ATU Sligo and a researcher with the HEA funded Project WAVE (**W**orking **T**owards **A**cademic and **V**ocational **E**quity), a PATH 4 Phase 2 initiative supporting students with intellectual

ATU Sligo

disabilities in Higher Education. Her teaching and research focus on inclusive pedagogy, co-learning, Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and creative visual methodologies.

Tamsin leads ATU's innovation in graphic facilitation, developing a Digital Badge completed by over 100 staff and now forming a vibrant community of practice across the university. This has facilitated ATU educators to rethink how they deliver text-heavy content, creating a more equitable, inclusive and accessible learning environment.

Her work extends beyond ATU through collaborations with community organisations exploring innovative, accessible approaches to support non-traditional learners. For example, Tamsin has explored the lived experiences of Irish Traveller communities in home and school environments.

Dr Cavaliero's initiatives connect students, staff, and community partners to co-create equitable, engaging learning environments and meaningful pathways into education, work and civic participation.

Dr Bairbre Tiernan

*Advancing the Development of an Inclusive Society
through Education*

Dr Bairbre Tiernan, SFHEA, Lecturer in the Centre for Special Education, Inclusion and Diversity (CSENID), Department of Education, ATU St Angelas, advocates for inclusion through her teaching and her research. Promoting inclusive education

ATU St. Angelas

in schools is a central tenet of her work. Currently, in response to the development of a more inclusive Irish education system, Dr Tiernan, with CSENID colleagues, is engaged in the Impact of a Special and Inclusive Teacher Education Professional Learning Programme on Special Education Teachers, Learners, and Schools project researching how specialised professional learning supports teachers to develop as inclusive practitioners and the cascade effect on schools.

Within the northwest region, she co-leads the National Council for Special Education (NCSE) project, namely the Research Based Project, which aims to build the research capacity and skills of practicing educators, and thereby, to enhance inclusive and special education teaching and learning experiences for all. She acts as a consultant to schools involved in the project, supporting the participants achieve their research goals.

Recently, Dr Tiernan was involved in the successful tendering process which resulted in the ATU providing a national training programme for Special Needs Assistants on behalf of NCSE, valued €1.9 million.

The ATU Teaching and Learning Centre and N-TUTORR: Empowering the University to Transform Learning

The ATU Teaching and Learning Centre at Atlantic Technological University (ATU) focuses on transformative education, sustainable learning futures, and advancing excellence in learning and teaching. The centre collaborates with over 2,500 academic and professional services staff across ATU's nine campuses. The centre supports university staff in developing their capabilities in teaching, learning, and assessment design. It guides the development of the curriculum, promotes excellence in teaching practices to enhance the student experience, and ensures robust academic standards.

A core enhancement project for ATU and the Teaching & Learning Centre from 2022-2025 was N-TUTORR. The National Technological University Transformation for Recovery and Resilience (N-TUTORR) project, an EU funded program overseen by the HEA value 40 million euro (7.3 million investment in ATU). N-TUTORR was designed to transform learning, teaching and assessment by focussing on transforming the student experience and developing the capabilities of all staff to address a sustainable pedagogical and learning environment with particular and critical focus on digital transformation, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI). This national programme of work was designed to enable and leverage digital transformations to achieve sustainable and long-lasting change in the higher education student experience. The programme aimed to implement and utilise digital technologies and platforms in a manner which enabled and empowered students and staff to enhance and develop their higher education experience.

Learn more about the project deliverables at: <https://ATU.ie/NTUTORR> plus the research outputs at: <https://www.atu.ie/about/teaching-and-learning/n-tutorr/n-tutorr-research-publications>. Further detail on the Teaching and Learning Centre at ATU is available at: <https://www.atu.ie/about/teaching-and-learning>

Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) at ATU

Atlantic Technological University (ATU) is committed to embedding Equality, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI) across teaching, research, professional practice, ensuring that all students and staff can learn and work in an environment defined by dignity, respect and fairness. Diversity is recognised as a strength that enhances creativity, innovation and academic excellence.

As a public body, ATU fulfils its obligations under the Irish Human Rights and Equality Commission Act (2014) and the Technological Universities Act (2018) as amended by the HEA Act (2022), integrating equality and human rights considerations into strategic planning, policy development and institutional decision-making. This includes promoting equality of opportunity, eliminating discrimination and protecting human rights across all university activities.

EDI at ATU is supported through institution-wide structures, including the Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Subcommittee of the Governing Body, the EDI Steering Group, the Athena Swan Self-Assessment Team and the Race Equality Working Group. Together, these groups guide the implementation of evidence-informed actions aligned with Irish equality legislation, compliance with national frameworks, international good practice and address structural inequalities.

Research plays a key role in advancing EDI at ATU, informing inclusive pedagogy, student support, staff development and policy implementation. This work is supported by Embedding Equality Diversity & Inclusion in the Curriculum of the new Technological University Sector (**EDIT**) Project Principles and Toolkit. Many ATU researchers contribute directly to national and European research on inclusion, wellbeing, access to education and social justice. Advancing equality, diversity and inclusion is a shared responsibility across ATU. Through collaboration, research and community engagement, ATU continues to build a safe, welcoming and inclusive university where everyone can contribute and thrive.

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